

A mapping of PhD dissertations inspired by critical mathematics education: Some voices from Brazil

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This article maps doctoral dissertations inspired by critical mathematics education that were produced by Épura- Research Group on Mathematics Education and Inclusion, from 2008 to 2020. We applied the inclusion criteria, using the descriptors “critical mathematics education”, “Skovsmose”, “landscapes of investigation”, and “social justice”, we selected 10 PhD dissertations to analyse. The results show an advance in research inspired by critical mathematics education in Brazil, which include concerns such as inclusion, dialogue, landscapes of investigation, work with projects, affirmative action policies for access to, and permanence, in higher education, and foregrounds, at different levels of education.

Introduction

Critical mathematics education is defined in terms of concerns that include political and social dimensions related to mathematics education. These concerns involve democracy, inclusion, exclusion, dialogue, social justice, equity, among others (Skovsmose, 2011). Brazil has experienced an increase in research that connects mathematics education and society and is inspired by critical mathematics education. This growth is expressed by the creation of research groups, publication of doctoral dissertations, and events based on this perspective, such as the Colloquium on Research in Critical Mathematics Education, held in Brazil in 2016, 2018 and 2019. This growth is followed by the need for studies that seek to map scientific production, critically analysing it and indicating possible trends.

This article maps doctoral dissertations inspired by critical mathematics education that were produced by the Épura Research Group on Mathematics Education and Inclusion, from 2008 to 2020. The group is based in the Post-Graduation Programme in Mathematics Education (PPGEM) of the São Paulo State University (UNESP), Campus of Rio Claro (SP, Brazil). The limitation of the database to this research group is justified for two reasons. The first, because the Épura Group is coordinated by Prof. Dr. Miriam Godoy Penteado and Prof.

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Dr. Ole Skovsmose, researchers recognised nationally and internationally for their contributions to critical mathematics education. The second reason is that researchers from the Épura group have dedicated themselves to developing research that contributes to the education of students from underrepresented groups. Thus, for theoretical and methodological support of what we propose to accomplish, the article is organised by this introduction, a methodology, presentation and analysis of the mapped PhD dissertations, and final considerations.

Methodology

The captions of research indicators: (1) Critical Mathematics Education, (2) Social Justice (3) Landscapes of Investigation (4) Skovsmose

Author	Title of the dissertation	1	2	3	4
Elielson R. de Sales (2013)	Visualisation in mathematics teaching: An experience with deaf students	-	x	-	x
Vanessa de Paula Cintra (2014)	Work with projects in the initial education of mathematics teachers from the perspective of inclusive education	-	x	-	x
Luciano F. Lima (2015)	Conversations on mathematics with seniors enabled by a university extension action	x	-	x	x
Renato Marcone Souza (2015)	Deficiencialism: the invention of disability by normality	-	x	-	x
Raquel Milani (2015)	The process prospective mathematics teachers' learning to dialogue with their students in the supervised teaching practice	x	-	x	x
Denival Biotto Filho (2015)	Who has never dreamt of being a football player? A work with projects to rework foregrounds	x	-	x	x
Guilherme H. Gomes Silva (2016)	Equity in access to and permanence in higher education: The role of mathematics education regarding affirmative action policies for underrepresented groups	x	x	-	x
João Luiz Muzinatti (2018)	The soothing "truth" in mathematics education: How middle-class students' arguments can reveal their view of social injustice	x	x	-	x
Ana Carolina Faustino (2018)	"How did you come to this result?": The dialogue in mathematics classes of the early years of elementary school)	x	x	x	x
Amanda Q. Moura (2020)	The encounter between the deaf and the hearing in landscapes of investigation: From uncertainties to possibilities in mathematics classes	x	x	x	x

Table 1: PhD dissertations of the Épura group that composes this study and descriptors present in the research.

We used a qualitative approach (Bogdan & Biklen, 1994) in a descriptive-analytical study. To achieve the objectives proposed, to map PhD dissertations in the field of critical mathematics education, we used state-of-the-art (Ferreira, 2002) or state-of-knowledge-type research, particularly demarcating investigations developed by the Épura research group, interrelated

as a web, from 2008, when the group was founded, through 2020. Therefore, the methodological approach chosen for the article supports the need to know in more detail the contexts, objectives, main results, and conclusions of the localised production of the knowledge. We located 11 PhD dissertations on the website of the Épura group, in which we applied as inclusion criteria the descriptors “critical mathematics education”, “Skovsmose”, “landscapes of investigation”, and “social justice”, and the condition that at least two of these descriptors were present in the text of the PhD dissertation. Thus, we selected 10 titles (Table 1) for reading and analysis.

To present the research mapped, we prepared an authorial guideline specifying the data extracted during the critical analysis of the texts. Namely: 1) study problem; 2) objectives; 3) study participants and location; 4) methodological approach; 5) methodological procedures; 6) theoretical framework; 7) main references and 8) results.

What do the PhD dissertations say? Some voices from Brazil

In this section the dissertations located are presented in the chronological sequence of defences, as given in Table 1.

Sales’ research (2013) was carried out in a public school in the city of Rio Claro/SP with eight 5th grade deaf students, users of the Brazilian Sign Language (Libras). The proposal was to analyse whether the resources that privilege visualisation contribute to teaching mathematics to deaf students through geometry activities. The researcher discusses mathematics education and its relations with inclusive education. He addresses the concept of empowerment in mathematics education, the construction of the concept of deafness, the visibility of the deaf person, and visualisation in mathematics education. He also analyses the importance of the sign language in this process.

The research is exploratory, descriptive and qualitative in nature. The tools used to produce data were the field notebook, filming and transcription, written records of the activities developed, documents, and semi-structured interviews with parents, students, teacher, and interpreter of sign language. The researcher developed a pedagogical intervention plan to create an environment for teaching and learning mathematics based on visual aspects for deaf students participating in the research. It is noteworthy that Libras was the language of instruction throughout the development of the intervention plan. The activities developed with the students were related to some geometric concepts and the identification of figures, to explore the visual-spatial thinking resulting from the manipulation and mental construction of relations between images, local and dynamic thinking. The researcher also conducted a survey with the students to gather information about some renowned paintings and artists who were inspired by mathematics. At the end of this stage, the students produced canvases. At the end of the intervention plan was a pedagogical excursion to an outstanding art museum and a cultural centre.

Sales (2013) emphasises that the movement made to develop the activities of the intervention plan meets the ideas of “empowerment” in mathematics education, i.e., students use mathematics to improve life chances, relating it to study, work, and more effective

participation in society through critical mathematical citizenship. Students, also, began to take a mathematical look at the world in which they were inserted, identifying points, lines, curves, maps, paths, for example. He identified four aspects of the students: curiosity, involvement, interaction, and interest in the activities. He also identified that “seeing, obtaining information to then perceive, visualise and understand”¹ (Sales, 2013, p. 160) is not something natural for anyone (whether deaf or not) and needs to be developed. In this sense, he verified the importance of the activities for the development of visuality, opportunities for the deaf students to expand their “way of looking”. Sales (2013) concludes that the participation in the intervention plan “affected” the way each participant thinks and acts towards geometry and brings a new meaning to the understanding of this area of knowledge in their personal and school life. The researcher states that working with activities planned to teach the deaf, combined with sign language, produced the involvement and mathematical development of the group of deaf students.

Cintra’s PhD dissertation (2014) is concerned about the initial formation of mathematics teachers for inclusive education. She mobilises concepts of critical mathematics education, such as work with projects and risk zones. The objective of the research was to investigate the involvement of 10 students from a mathematics teaching degree course when creating and executing research projects that addressed inclusive education. Based on a qualitative approach, data production was carried out in two mandatory classes, called “Project Development I” and “Project Development II”, taught by the author of the dissertation, in the mathematics degree course of a public university in the state of Minas Gerais. During the first, students were divided into four groups and created projects that involved the following themes: the contributions of technology for students with hearing impairment to learn mathematics; the transcription process of mathematics books to Braille; the identification of deaf students’ difficulties in logical reasoning activities in an urban school; the creation and application of geometric materials for students with visual impairment to learn mathematics.

In “Project Development II”, the students visited schools that serve students with disabilities and an institute of pedagogical support for students with visual impairment and, after having developed the projects in schools in the city, prepared a final report, which was configured as part of the research data, along with the final version of the project and questionnaires with open questions each student in the study answered. The questionnaires aimed to know the students, their motivations for choosing the project theme, aspects of project preparation and execution, and preparation of the final report. In a complementary way, the author used the field diary. The data analysis was based on content analysis and two categories were constructed. In the first, the author discusses students’ learning in the construction of projects and in the second, she addresses aspects of teacher education and mathematics education. The results of the research show that the preparation and execution of a project that connects mathematics education and inclusion contributes to the students

¹ “ver, obter informações para, então, perceber, visualizar e compreender” (Sales, 2013, p. 160).

in mathematics teaching degree course changing their conceptions regarding inclusion. Initially, students expressed feelings of pity and willingness to help people with disabilities., Through contact with the literature in the area of inclusion and with experiences in schools, students began to recognise people with disabilities as beings with rights and duties, rights that include learning mathematics, as they are able to overcome obstacles and learn in a school together with other students.

Lima (2015) investigated an extension action² that aimed to foster conversations about mathematics with senior people. The research question sought to answer: What do we reveal in a university extension action involving conversations on mathematics with senior people? To this end, the researcher engaged with theoretical references in the field of critical mathematics education, justifying the relevance of the study based on the low proportionality of extension activities with senior people in Brazil, specifically related to mathematics. The context of data production involved a group of seniors over 50 years of age participating in the activity fortnightly for one year. Each meeting lasted approximately one hour. The problematisation of mathematical dialogues had subjects such as loans, Moebius range, numerical regularities and symmetries, drawn from a variable set of resources. The methodological approach adopted was qualitative and the instruments used were the field diary and interview with eight members of the group participating in the mathematical conversations.

Particularly, with regard to mathematics education and the possibilities of educational projects for the seniors, the author states that activities of this nature can contribute to the strengthening of the formation and maintenance of affective ties and to intellectual habits through improving coexistence and interaction between peers (Lima, 2015). The methodological section of the dissertation describes the participants' productions, data from the researcher's field diary, way of analysing the results, as well as the respondents' characterisation.

Lima argues that the interactive possibility resulting from the analysis demonstrates that two themes are essential for the guiding question of the PhD dissertation, namely: 1) motivation to remain in action; and 2) ways of seniors' participation in mathematical conversations. The reasons relate to the fact that the tasks exposed, debated, and reflected seniors' cognition. There is extensive social interaction among all, and this leads to new learning. The group surveyed showed they liked and craved learning mathematics. The conclusions highlight elements that are strong indicators for future work with senior education, namely: Financial Education for Senior Citizens; Mathematics and Art; Games and Mathematics, among others.

² In Brazil, the epistemic basis of Universities is consolidated in activities that involve Teaching, Research and Extension. Extension actions aim to dialogue with social sectors in order to contribute to problems that emerge from the context of daily experience and work of people without a hierarchical relationship. We can understand the extension as being communication practices between University-Society in order to share plural knowledge (scientific-cultural) in which the participants can experience teaching and research processes so that the knowledge is complementary.

Souza (2015) investigated inclusion in the light of the concept of deficiencialism, which is elaborated by him in the dissertation. When referring to “deficiencialism”, in the journey through theories, this term is analysed from postcolonial perspectives emphasizing the constitution of the colonised subject. For him, “The construction of the colonised subject is then an effect of stereotyping discourse, and I understand that the construction of other excluded subjects, other excluded groups, is done in a similar way” (Souza, 2015, p. 52). The dissertation advances the discussion of the stereotype in relation to disability, highlighting elements of colonial studies in which Fanon is an inspiration to think about the field of disability. In analogy to Fanon’s statement in “Black skin, white masks” that “The black man wants to be like the white man. For the black man there is only one destiny. And it is White.” (Fanon, 2008, cited on p. 53), the researcher understands that “in something similar, a kind of anti-deficiencialism, we could adapt this phrase saying that the disabled person wants to be normal and, for her, there is really only one destination: normality” (p. 53)³.

In the dissertation, episodes of empirical data production in the context of Brazil and India are highlighted. One of the papers refers to a situation experienced by the author when he participated in a “Teacher Qualification Course in the Vision Impairment Area”, offered via Instituto Benjamin Constant (IBC) in Rio de Janeiro (RJ), a school for the education of visually impaired people in Brazil. In addition, reflections are presented on the experience in which Souza (2015) interviewed professionals from the National Association for the Blind (NAB) in Mumbai, India. In summary, the researcher concludes that the post-colonial perspective contributed as a tactical element to resist the classifications of disability and its forms of understanding throughout history. According to the author, the central action of post-colonialism would be to rewrite colonial narratives from the perspective of the colonised, such as the case of Carlos, a student with disability. As the concept of “deficiencialism” is understood in the work as “the networks of stereotypes used to define abnormalities in the face of normality, thinking of people with disabilities, it is natural that the notion of anti-deficiencialism and post-deficiencialism arises” (Souza, 2015, p. 149)⁴.

Milani (2015) chose as a question of his qualitative research: how do prospective mathematics teachers and students learn to dialogue during their supervised teaching practice? To answer his question, Milani (2015) listed as an objective to propose and evaluate actions to promote dialogue learning in teacher education. The participants in the research were two prospective teachers the researcher followed during their teaching practice. The text focuses on the concept of dialogue in landscapes of investigation by Helle Alrø and Ole Skovsmose, characterising their theoretical and empirical aspects that permeate the entire PhD dissertation. Thus, Milani (2015) introduces the definition of dialogue according to these

³ “em algo similar, uma espécie de anti-deficiencialismo, poderíamos adaptar tal frase dizendo que a pessoa com deficiência quer ser normal e, para ela, há realmente apenas um destino: a normalidade” (Souza, 2015, p. 53).

⁴ “as redes de estereótipos utilizadas com o intuito de definir os anormais perante uma normalidade, pensando em pessoas com deficiência, é natural que surja a noção de anti-deficiencialismo e a de pós-deficiencialismo” (Souza, 2015, p. 149).

authors, i.e., a type of conversation with some special characteristics that aims at critical learning. The researcher reflects on the action of asking questions in mathematics classes and proposes to insert dialogic questions as another element of dialogue. The data was produced during the third set of classes of supervised teaching practice in mathematics, which includes in the syllabus the teaching performance in mathematics in high school classes involving diagnosis, planning, execution, and evaluation during the prospective teachers' classes, and the discussion between the supervisor teacher and the prospective teacher. The instruments were of two types: written and audio records. The practice that was developed in that discipline was a collective practice of the researcher and the teaching practice teacher. The activities were prepared for the development of the discipline and provided information on how the prospective teachers thought and practised the dialogue.

As a result, Milani (2015) lists some actions that can be part of learning to dialogue by future teachers with their students: experience dialogue in investigative activities; recognise themselves as people in dialogue; imagine themselves as teachers in dialogue; explain the concerns that emerge in this process of imagination, reflect on them and look for solutions; create imaginary dialogues, predicting speeches and actions of those involved; transform more closed communication patterns into more dialogic interactions; and engage in moments of guidance with the supervisor teacher. In the final considerations the researcher presents her definition of dialogue: "it is a form of interaction between teacher and students, engaged in a learning activity, in which speech and active listening are shared, ideas are discussed and the understanding of what the other says is fundamental" (Milani, 2015, p.202)⁵. She emphasises that the choice to dialogue in mathematics education is not neutral.

Biotto Filho's PhD dissertation (2015) investigated the re-elaboration of children's foregrounds, in a non-formal educational environment, based on the pedagogical approach of working with projects. According to the author, "foreground" means the future horizons of a person, or group of people, and can generate intentions and reasons for students to engage or not in school activities, such as those involving mathematics. In the theoretical framework, the author mobilises concepts of critical mathematics education such as foreground, work with projects, arranged situation, and border position. Based on a qualitative methodology, data production was carried out in a semi-boarding school social institution that children from six to twelve years of age attended in the school counter-shift. Thus, in his choice of the context for data production, the author considered not only the existing situation (traditionally organised school), or the ideal situation (school based on the perspective of work with projects), but an arranged situation, in which he developed activities during 11 meetings, based on the approach of work with projects in the semi-boarding school with 11 children aged around 11 years old, i.e., school age. These meetings were followed by interviews.

⁵ "É uma forma de interação entre professor e alunos, engajados em uma atividade de aprendizagem, em que a fala e a escuta ativa são compartilhadas, ideias são discutidas e a compreensão do que o outro diz é fundamental" (Milani, 2015, p.202).

The project activities involved two phases: introducing the theming phase and the student group research phase. In the first, the participants chose to work with the football theme, related to the aspect of becoming a football player. The second phase involved dividing the students into three groups that researched the themes football, future, and professions. Afterwards, at the end of the project, each group presented its final product. Seeking to read the students' foregrounds, the author conducted interviews, inspired by the concept of InterView, which took the form of a structured conversation between interviewer and interviewee in which both look together at the subject of the conversation, negotiate meanings, and the interviewee participates in the interpretation of the data. Another important aspect of this process was the search to understand the elements present in the students' backgrounds, as well as the social context in which they live. The results of this study show the interpretative character of the foregrounds and point out the possibilities of investigating them by reading between views. It is also evidenced that the activities with projects contribute to the re-elaboration of foregrounds.

Silva's research (2016) sought to understand how mathematics education could contribute to the permanence and progress of students who benefited from affirmative action policies of higher education courses in the exact sciences. The theoretical framework used was mathematics education for social justice and critical mathematics education. The study participants were managers/professors of higher education and students who benefited from affirmative action policies in the exact sciences of two federal universities in Brazil. The investigation had a qualitative approach, was inspired by the case study, and the researcher conducted documentary analysis and semi-structured interviews, keeping a field notebook during the interviews. The data analysis was based on content analysis and critical survey. At the end of the research, Silva (2016) emphasises that even if it is not enough, the Quota Law is of paramount importance to combat social injustices and inequities present in society. Affirmative action contributes to students' access and permanence in public universities.

Silva (2016) argues that mathematics education can help students who intend to enter (access) and those who are already attending (permanence). For example, mathematics can be used as a "filter" to select people who meet the university's criteria through the selection process and, at the same time, the student who understands the "dominant" knowledge can be selected to win a scholarship, i.e., mathematical literacy can be a means to open doors. Aware of this, many of the students in the study who entered through the quotas, at the end of the course, returned to their cities to teach mathematics classes, voluntarily, in community courses, to help other students to enter higher education. Silva (2016) stresses that quota students reported having suffered microaggressions in the classroom from teachers and colleagues. Microaggressions can have consequences such as, for example, withdrawal from the course, anxiety, and depression. The researcher points out that affirmative action are more than mere welfare action; it aims to improve students' access to permanence and their social and academic integration, for a more just and equitable society, overcoming microaggressions and other forms of prejudice and discrimination they suffer.

Faustino's research (2018) sought to understand how teachers and students dialogue in mathematics classes in the early years of elementary school, thus seeking to identify elements that favour the construction of a dialogic mathematics class. The theoretical framework used was critical mathematics education, mathematics education for social justice, and critical pedagogy. The study participants were two teachers from the 3rd and 5th grades of elementary school, in interaction with their students in a public school in the state of São Paulo – Brazil. The research had a qualitative approach, based on participant observation and during data production, the researcher, together with the teachers, developed the project entitled “Environment and Mathematics”. This project was developed with students from both classes during one semester. The project focused on the content of quantities and measures. The tasks included, for example, producing videos in which mathematics was used to interpret environmental issues such as the use of water in school and students' homes. The dialogues established between teachers and students during mathematics classes were registered in field diaries, through audio and video-recordings.

At the end of the research, Faustino (2018) advocates that the way the teacher organises the learning environment influences the pattern of communication that will emerge. Dialogue emerged during the project activities, in which students had to make decisions and share their perspectives. At this point, aspects such as investigating, presenting arguments, taking risks, and building equity were identified in the interactions. The author emphasises that interactions in classes are not free of conflicts (existence of non-dialogical acts). Finally, Faustino (2018) emphasises that teachers must listen actively, moving epistemologically to understand children's perspectives, to subsequently ask questions that help them understand the concepts.

Muzinatti (2018) described and identified specific particularities of the thinking and ideology of 7th-grade students (aged between 11 and 13 years) in a middle/upper class of a school in São Paulo, also constituted and confirmed in mathematics classes. In the theoretical framework, the researcher seeks to understand how the so-called “truth of numbers” may be reaching elementary school students, more precisely the students participating in the research. To understand the paths by which this absolute truth travels from ancient Athens to the classrooms of today, the researcher presents some pre-Socratic influences and aspects of Platonism that pervade antiquity, the medieval, the so-called modernity. He also shows the idea of Truth that has surpassed the centuries, poured into the religions, and philosophers' offices. Finally, the researcher presents Nietzsche's thought and the contextualisation of such questioning through critical mathematics education as the most fundamental critique.

The data was produced from activities planned and developed by the researcher which were recorded. Muzunatti (2018) chose to describe the classroom episodes as three short stories with researcher and students as the characters. To analyse the data, the author reflects on the students' arguments, their postures towards situations related to social injustices, and

the role of mathematics education in their construction of world representation. Coming from the entire historical process of reinforcing mathematics as absolute truth, the effect of Platonism that shapes the West, this perspective reproduced in academia is also perceived in the speech of the students participating in the research. It highlights the relationship of power and exclusion that mathematics exercises within the participating group, and even within the family, showing that in the classroom, distinction and respectability accompany those who excel in learning numbers. When the researcher, aiming for students to interpret the world via numbers, brings an overview of the reality, he imagined that mathematical “inexorability” would be a decisive factor in argumentation. However, students did not seem to be touched by the information: they treated it as something normal or, at worst, a fatality. The social problems revealed by the numbers do not seem to sensitise them. Contrary to what the researcher expected, the numbers did not help to sensitise students to the Brazilian social reality.

Moura (2020) raises the topic of inclusive education by emphasising the importance of dialogue in landscapes of investigation. The participants in her study were deaf and hearing students, the interpreter teacher of sign language, and the regular teacher in a class of the initial years of elementary school. Her research aimed to understand the interactions in mathematics classes in which they study deaf and hearing, in an approach of landscapes of investigation. This approach brings as its main characteristic the openness to different forms of learning through dialogue. In the theoretical framework, the researcher mobilises concepts arising from critical pedagogy such as tolerance and dialogue; critical mathematics education, such as landscapes of investigation, microexclusion, deficiencialism, and meetings amongst differences; and mathematics education for social justice, such as reading and writing the world with mathematics and culturally relevant pedagogy.

The research was based on a qualitative approach, used participant observation, and the data was produced in a public school in the state of São Paulo, in a regular classroom of the 5th grade. Three teachers, three interpreters of signal language, and the 17 students of the class, of which 12 were hearing and five were deaf, participated in the research. The classes were recorded with audio and video, and then episodes were transcribed and analysed. In these classes, students engaged in inclusive landscapes of investigation that were developed by the researcher and the teachers. The results of Moura’s research (2020) show that dialogue was a fundamental aspect of the students’ inclusion and that it involved elements such as decentralisation, active listening, and the presence of dialogic acts, which proved to be fundamental for cooperation between the deaf and the hearing. The author emphasises how important it is to understand that inclusive education is an encounter of differences and that people value and respect those differences in mathematics classes, recognising them as a valuable resource for teaching and learning. According to the researcher, landscapes of investigation created opportunities for cooperation and the construction of equity through dialogue, which is fundamental in the development of inclusive actions.

Considerations

The results show an advance in research inspired by critical mathematics education in Brazil, which include concerns such as inclusion, dialogue, landscapes of investigation, work with projects, affirmative action policies and foregrounds, at different levels of education. All studies analysed were based on qualitative methodologies and are practice-based methodologies. The data from the fieldwork of the studies by Sales (2013), Souza (2015), Muzinatti (2018), Faustino (2018), and Moura (2020) were produced in schools of basic education; by Cintra (2014), Milani (2015), and Silva (2016) in undergraduate courses in mathematics; by Biotto Filho (2015) in a semi-boarding school institution that served school-age children; while Lima's (2015) research was intended for senior citizens. Thus, the research studies are strongly committed to understanding and changing the Brazilian school reality at different levels of education, as well as in the different spaces where educational processes can take place. Such commitment is not restricted only to formal educational spaces, but also to non-formal spaces and seeks to contemplate different groups of students.

The experience of contact with the studies in this paper indicates that the Épura Group's research represents a collective effort to address issues related to mathematics education and society in the Brazilian context. The research studies present dialogue as central source of the promotion of communication, cooperation, and investigation in mathematics classes in different – formal and informal – educational spaces, and indicate the relevance of thinking of mathematics as a tool of social inclusion of children, young people and adults.

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